

Oxovanadium(IV) complexes of Schiff base derived from 3-aminopropanol and derivatives of salicylaldehyde

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Abstract : Oxovanadium(IV) complexes were synthesised by reacting vanadyl acetylacetonate with Schiff bases obtained by condensation of 3-aminopropanol with salicylaldehyde and its derivatives, 3-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and 3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde. The complexes were characterised by IR and UV-Visible spectra. The effects of the substituents on salicylaldehyde and the changes in electronic spectra in different solvents with respect to donor properties of the solvents were studied. The reaction of the complexes with hydrogen peroxide was also observed.

Keywords : Schiff base, oxovanadium(IV), salicylaldehyde.

Introduction

The vanadium dependent haloperoxidase, the nitrogenases, other biologically active vanadium dependent compounds, their structural and other functional models have increased the interest in the coordination chemistry of vanadium¹⁻³. The structural features of the vanadium haloperoxidases are independent of their origin and the oxovanadium core is present in a O₃N coordinating environment and the overall geometry is trigonal bipyramidal^{4,5}.

Attempts have been made to reproduce enzymatic functions of VHPOs by use of tridentate Schiff's bases and tetradentate Schiff's bases ligands of tripode type as model ligands^{6,7}. The complexes used for asymmetric catalytic reactions involved tetradentate Schiff's base ligands derived from 1,2-diamines and salicylaldehyde⁸. In continuation^{9,10} to our attempts to prepare model compounds of vanadium haloperoxidase, we report the oxovanadium(IV) Schiff's base complexes derived from 3-aminopropanol, salicylaldehyde and its 3-methoxy, 5-nitro, 5-chloro and 3,5-dichloro derivatives, characterized in solid state and in solution. The donor ability effects¹¹ of the solvent on the compositions and coordination geometries of the complexes, stability of peroxo complexes and the effect of the substituents in the ligands have been discussed.

Experimental

Vanadium pentoxide, 3-aminopropanol, salicylaldehyde and its 3-methoxy; 5-nitro; 5-chloro and 3,5-dichloro derivatives were of Sigma. The other chemicals used were of analytical grade. VO(acac)₂ was synthesised from V₂O₅ as given in the literature¹².

Analysis : A Perkin-Elmer series II, CHNS Analyzer, model 2400 at the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Kolkata, was used for C, H, N microanalyses. Vanadium was estimated by titration with a Fe²⁺ solution in the presence of sulphonated diphenylamine as indicator, after decomposing the sample with sodium peroxide¹³.

The UV-Vis spectra were recorded in DMSO solution using Shimadzu 2401 PC and the IR spectra in KBr pellets with Perkin-Elmer L 120-00A FT-IR spectrometer.

Ligand : The Schiff's bases were obtained by condensation of 3-aminopropanol with salicylaldehyde and its derivatives, were not isolated in solid state. 1.50 ml (20 mmol) 3-aminopropanol and 2.85 ml (20 mmol) salicylaldehyde mixed in a 100 ml round bottom flask and refluxed it for 3 h. Dichloromethane (20 ml) was used as solvent. The color of the resulting solution turns yellow. Similarly the derivatives of salicylaldehyde were taken with 3-aminopropanol. 3.04 g (20 mmol) of 3-methoxy salicylaldehyde and 1.50 ml (20 mmol) of 3-aminopropanol was refluxed in dichloromethane (20 ml) for 3 h. The solution turns yellow. 3.34 g (20 mmol) 5-nitrosali-

cylaldehyde, 3.12 g (20 mmol) of 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and 3.82 g (20 mmol) 3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde were taken for ligand synthesis with 1.50 ml (20 mmol) of 3-aminopropanol in 20 ml dichloromethane for ligand synthesis. In all the cases the solution turns yellow after reflux.

Preparation of the complexes :

[VO(Sal-ap)] (1) : 10 mmol of VO(acac)₂ (2.65 g) in CH₂Cl₂ was added to resulting yellow solution containing the Schiff base obtained by condensation of 3-aminopropanol and salicylaldehyde (represented as Sal-ap). The resultant mixture was refluxed for 2 h under nitrogen atmosphere. The color of the solution first turns blue and gradually changed to green. The dark green complex [VO(Sal-ap)] (1) was isolated by first reducing the volume of the solution under reduced pressure and then by adding diethylether. The complex was recrystallised from CH₂Cl₂ solution. Yield : 0.854 g, 35% (Found : V, 20.44; C, 50.00; H, 4.62; N, 5.56. Calcd. complex 1 with formula weight 244.1 (C₁₀H₁₁O₃NV) : V, 20.87; C, 49.16; H, 4.54; N, 5.74%).

[VO(3-methoxy-Sal-ap)] (2) : 10 mmol of VO(acac)₂ (2.65 g) in CH₂Cl₂ was added to resulting yellow solution containing the Schiff's base obtained by condensation, by refluxing the mixture of 3.04 g (20 mmol) of 3-methoxy salicylaldehyde and 1.50 ml (20 mmol) of 3-aminopropanol in dichloromethane (20 ml) for 3 h. The resultant mixture of VO(acac)₂ and the Schiff's base was refluxed for 2 h under nitrogen atmosphere. The color of the solution first turns blue and gradually changed to green. The dark green complex [VO(3-methoxy-Sal-ap)] (2) was isolated by first reducing the volume of the solution under reduced pressure and then by adding diethyl ether. The complex was recrystallised from CH₂Cl₂ solution. Yield : 1.150 g, 42% (Found : V, 18.24; C, 48.46; H, 4.58; N, 5.31. Calcd. for complex 2 with formula weight 274.1 (C₁₁H₁₃O₄NV) : V, 18.59; C, 48.16; H, 4.78; N, 5.11%).

[VO(5-nitro-Sal-ap)] (3) : 10 mmol of VO(acac)₂ (2.65 g) in CH₂Cl₂ was added to resulting yellow solution containing the Schiff's base obtained by condensation, by refluxing the mixture of 3.34 g (20 mmol) of 5-nitro salicylaldehyde and 1.50 ml (20 mmol) of 3-aminopropanol in dichloromethane (20 ml) for 3 h. The resultant mixture of VO(acac)₂ and the Schiff's base was refluxed for 2 h under nitrogen atmosphere. The color of the solution first turns blue and gradually changed to green. The dark green complex [VO(5-nitro-Sal-ap)] (3) was isolated by first reducing the volume of the solution under reduced

pressure and then by adding diethyl ether. The complex was recrystallised from CH₂Cl₂ solution. Yield : 1.150 g, 42% (Found : V, 17.35; C, 41.46; H, 3.58; N, 9.83. Calcd. values for complex 3 with formula weight 289.0 (C₁₀H₁₀O₅N₂V) : V, 17.63; C, 41.53; H, 3.49; N, 9.69%).

[VO(5-chloro-Sal-ap)] (4) : 10 mmol of VO(acac)₂ (2.65 g) in CH₂Cl₂ was added to resulting yellow solution containing the Schiff's base obtained by condensation, by refluxing the mixture of 3.12 g (20 mmol) of 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and 1.50 ml (20 mmol) of 3-aminopropanol in dichloromethane (20 ml) for 3 h. The resultant mixture VO(acac)₂ and the Schiff's base was refluxed for 2 h under nitrogen atmosphere. The color of the solution first turns blue and gradually changed to green. The dark green complex [VO(5-chloro-Sal-ap)] (4) was isolated by first reducing the volume of the solution under reduced pressure and then by adding diethyl ether. The complex was recrystallised from CH₂Cl₂ solution. Yield : 1.251 g, 44% (Found : V, 18.36; C, 44.12; H, 3.59; N, 5.18. Calcd. values for complex 4 with formula weight 278.5 (C₁₀H₁₀O₃NVCl) : V, 18.29; C, 43.09; H, 3.62; N, 5.03%).

[VO(3,5-dichloro-Sal-ap)] (5) : 10 mmol of VO(acac)₂ (2.65 g) in CH₂Cl₂ was added to resulting yellow solution containing the Schiff's base obtained by condensation, by refluxing the mixture of 3.82 g (20 mmol) 3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde and 1.50 ml (20 mmol) of 3-aminopropanol in dichloromethane (20 ml) for 3 h. The resultant mixture of VO(acac)₂ and the Schiff's base was refluxed for 2 h under nitrogen atmosphere. The color of the solution first turns blue and gradually changed to green. The dark green complex [VO(3,5-dichloro-Sal-ap)] (5) was isolated by first reducing the volume of the solution under reduced pressure and then by adding diethyl ether. The complex was recrystallised from CH₂Cl₂ solution. Yield : 1.16 g, 37% (Found : V, 18.62; C, 38.88; H, 3.09; N, 4.58. Calcd. values for complex 5 with formula weight 313.1 (C₁₀H₉O₃NVCl₂) : V, 18.28; C, 38.35; H, 2.89; N, 4.48%).

Results and discussion

All the complexes are dark green, stable in air at room temperature, soluble in common organic solvents like CHCl₃, CH₃OH, CH₂Cl₂ and (CH₃)₂SO. The solution initially colored green and gradually turned to orange color on long standing (24 h).

The infrared absorption bands of the complexes (1-5) are, $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ in cm⁻¹ 962, 965, 888, 885, 908; $\nu(\text{V}-\text{O}-\text{V})$

cm^{-1} are 897, 863, 848, 832, 790. The very strong absorption bands in the range $885\text{--}965\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the complexes are assigned to V=O stretching vibrations. The appearance of the $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ frequencies below 990 cm^{-1} for all these oxovanadium(IV) complexes, suggests¹⁴ that in all the five complexes, the central vanadium atom is hexacoordinated. The asymmetric stretching vibrations (ν_a) for M-O(OXO)-M frequency is observed¹⁵ in the range $730\text{--}827\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the oxo bridged complexes of Mn^{3+} and Fe^{3+} . Hence, the other strong band in the range $790\text{--}897\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for all the complexes may be assigned to asymmetric stretching vibrations (ν_a) due to V-O (alkoxy oxygen)-V. Hence, it can be inferred from the IR spectra that in all the complexes, vanadium is hexacoordinated in the solid state, likely by forming polymeric vanadium oxygen (--V-O-V-O--) units¹⁴.

The UV-Vis spectra of the complexes in DMSO ($1 \times 10^{-3}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) (1) = salicylaldehyde (sal), (2) = 3-methoxysal, (3) = 5-nitrosal, (4) = 5-chlorosal, (5) = 3,5-dichlorosal, have been presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of the complexes in DMSO ($1 \times 10^{-3}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$).

The absorption bands in the UV-region around 375 nm, vary as ligands with different substituents are used. The CT band is not observed in the nitrosubstituent (3), probably due to higher electron withdrawing capacity of the nitro group. Fig. 2 exhibits the change in absorbance frequency of the complex 1, with respect to time (at an interval of 5 min). The absorption around 375 nm shifts to lower region while that around 325 nm shifts to higher wavelength.

The above observations can be explained in relation with the donor strength of the solvents used for recording the spectra. The complexes in the solid state exist as

Fig. 2. Absorption band complex 1 in DMSO in interval of 5 min.

dimers but in solvents, having strong donor properties, the V-O-V bond breaks up and the solvent itself satisfies the coordination position, vacated by the breaking of the oxo bridge. The band around 375 nm shifts to the shorter wavelength with time, which may be assigned due to the charge transfer from the alkoxy oxygen to vanadium(IV) in both monomer and dimer. It is expected that the extent of the charge transfer from oxygen to V^{IV} is stronger in the monomer with the V-O bond than in the dimer with V-O-V bond. The band at approximately 325 nm, the intensity of which increases with time, is probably attributed to the charge transfer from DMSO to V^{IV} in the monomer. That is, the direction of the change in intensity of both bands indicate the decomposition of the dimer to the monomer in polar solvent DMSO (donor number $D_N = 29.8$) with much higher donor ability¹¹ than that of inert solvent dichloromethane ($D_N = 0$).

Reactions with peroxide : The spectra of the complex 1 in dichloromethane, acetone, methanol solution in presence of peroxide exhibit new broad bands in the range $420\text{--}500\text{ nm}$. The new bands may be assigned due to charge transfer from O_2^{2-} to vanadium(V). But this band is absent in DMSO system. This is probably due to the strong bonding of DMSO with vanadium. As the donor number of the solvent increases, the bond strength of the solvent with vanadium increases.

Conclusion :

From the above discussions we can conclude that the complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{sal-ap})]$, exist as a dimer in dichloromethane, while it appears in mononuclear form in polar solvents like DMSO and methanol with one solvent molecule coordinating to vanadium in the equatorial plane. The stability of peroxo complexes is dependent on the donor ability of the solvent molecules. Greater the donor

ability of the solvent, weaker will be peroxo complexes. Hence, the proposed structure of the complexes will be as given below :

(Monomer)

(Dimer)

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